

Prediction of Household Income and Expenditure Using Data Mining

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ABSTRACT- Data mining is a field of computer technology which is useful for extracting and coming across styles in big information set. Its miles very usually carried out to any shape of large facts set or processing of information which incorporates collection, extraction and analysis in addition to any utility of pc decision guide device. The statistics mining discover the more than one agencies the information, which could then be used to reap greater prediction consequences by means of way of a selection help machine. Records mining can be implemented to expect the household profits and charges so that you can be beneficial in dealing with the expenses in the future. This paper shows special class algorithms of facts mining used to expand a information mining version for predictions of charges and income taking instructional qualification and variety of people incomes within the family because the base.

Keywords—income, expenditure, total earning people, WEKA tool.

I. Introduction

One of the main issues that the families are facing now a days are the effective management of the expenses. One who manages the expenses are considered as an ideal person in the society. The principle goal of the proposed gadget is to find out whether or not any sample inside the to be had facts and mine them which might also assist to expect the fees primarily based on their instructional qualifications. Facts mining is a multidisciplinary field masking facts era, device getting to know, information, pattern recognition, information retrieval, neural networks, records structures, artificial intelligence and records visualization. The software of statistics mining is not unusual inside the prediction of economic region. Financial data mining is an emerging field that can be effectively applied in the economic field. It uses numerous thoughts and concept, like category and clustering. When used effectively, a massive amount of financial data can be driven for analysis and modelling to help in effective planning, decision-making for the future.

II. Relationship between Household income and expenditure

A. Economic Division

The economic and social diversions and charge variance typically purpose modifications in monetary and social measurement which might be related to the overall boom of the citizen . The variant in expenditure, spending among families or even their academic qualification will finally affect variations in human way of life. There could be a huge difference among the rich and the poor. center elegance and

poor humans tends to be affected extra in this example. despite the fact that their profits is low, there can be extra charges which may affect their monetary balance.

B. Relationship

Income can be from any sources varying from agricultural sector to high scale industrial sector. Even though income depends on many factors, most probably educational standards can be a major factor affecting the whole more the educational level less the poverty or expenses.

But there are some common cause for the expenses. this includes the education, stationary requirements, day to day needs and emergency situations like hospital cases, which is unpredictable. This irregular expenses can result in a very complicated situations for the poor families.

II. ANALYZING DATA

In order to research facts we need to comply with some pre requirements. There is a want to gather the right dataset at the primary. After amassing the dataset we need to offer the information to a statistics mining algorithm. Therefore deciding on a records mining device follows the dataset series. After imparting the enough facts to the information mining device, use numerous algorithms to evaluate the outcomes.

III. Data Collection

Detailed income and expenses are collected. Main parameters include the Monthly household income, Monthly household expenses, Number of family members, EMI or rent amount. Annual household income, highest qualified member in the family and class. All the data excluding the highest qualified member and class is numeric. Data set is collected in an excel sheet.

1	MthlyHHir	MthlyHHE	NoofFlyM	EmiorRen	AnnualHH	HighestQu	NoofEarni	class
2	5000	8000	3	2000	64200	UnderGra	1	no
3	6000	7000	2	3000	79920	Illiterate	1	no
4	10000	4500	2	0	112800	UnderGra	1	yes
5	10000	2000	1	0	97200	Illiterate	1	yes
6	12500	12000	2	3000	147000	Graduate	1	yes
7	14000	8000	2	0	196560	Graduate	1	yes
8	15000	16000	3	35000	167400	PostGradu	1	no
9	18000	20000	5	8000	216000	Graduate	1	no
10	19000	9000	2	0	218880	UnderGra	1	yes
11	20000	9000	4	0	220800	UnderGra	2	yes
12	20000	18000	4	8000	278400	UnderGra	2	yes
13	22000	25000	6	12000	279840	Illiterate	1	no
14	23400	5000	3	0	292032	illiterate	1	yes
15	24000	10500	6	0	316800	Graduate	2	yes
16	24000	10000	4	0	244800	Graduate	2	yes
17	25000	12300	3	0	246000	Graduate	1	yes
18	25000	20000	3	3500	261000	Graduate	1	yes
19	25000	10000	6	0	258000	UnderGra	3	yes
20	29000	6600	2	2000	348000	Graduate	1	yes
21	30000	13000	4	0	385200	Graduate	1	yes
22	30500	25000	5	5000	351360	UnderGra	1	yes
23	32000	15000	4	0	445440	Professio	1	yes
24	34000	19000	6	0	330480	Professio	1	yes
25	34000	25000	3	4000	469200	Professio	1	yes
26	35000	12000	3	0	466200	Graduate	1	yes

Fig.1. Dataset that is used for the implementations.

27	35000	25000	4	0	449400	Professio	2	yes
28	39000	8000	4	0	556920	UnderGra	1	yes
29	40000	10000	4	0	412800	UnderGra	1	yes
30	42000	15000	4	0	488880	Graduate	1	yes
31	43000	12000	4	0	619200	Graduate	1	yes
32	45000	25000	6	0	523800	Graduate	3	yes
33	45000	40000	6	3500	507600	Professio	2	yes
34	45000	10000	2	1000	437400	PostGradu	1	yes
35	45000	22000	4	2500	610200	PostGradu	1	yes
36	46000	25000	5	3500	596160	Graduate	1	yes
37	47000	15000	7	0	456840	Professio	4	yes
38	50000	20000	4	0	570000	Professio	1	yes
39	50500	20000	3	0	581760	Professio	2	yes
40	55000	45000	6	12000	600600	Graduate	2	yes
41	60000	10000	3	0	590400	PostGradu	1	yes
42	60000	50000	6	10000	590400	Graduate	1	yes
43	65000	20000	4	5000	647400	Illiterate	2	yes
44	70000	9000	2	0	756000	Graduate	1	yes
45	80000	20000	4	0	1075200	Graduate	1	yes
46	85000	25000	5	0	1142400	UnderGra	2	yes
47	90000	48000	7	0	885600	PostGradu	3	yes
48	98000	25000	5	0	1152480	Professio	2	yes
49	100000	30000	6	0	1404000	Graduate	3	yes
50	100000	50000	4	20000	1032000	Professio	2	yes
51	100000	40000	6	10000	1320000	PostGradu	1	yes
52								

Fig.2. Dataset

The next step is to create the corresponding CSV file of the Dataset. CSV(Comma Separated Value) format will lay the data in a table of rows and columns and a comma is used to separate values on a row.

After creating the CSV file , we will convert the corresponding file into arff file(Attribute Relation File Format) , where a header is used that provides metadata about the data types in the columns. The arff file will be processed in the Weka tool for data processing and classification.

C. WEKA Tool

WEKA- which is an open source software which provides tools for data preprocessing, implementation of several Machine Learning algorithms which we use in our day to day life , and visualization tools so that you can develop machine

learning techniques and apply them to real-world data mining problems to extract the required patterns and apply them.

Fig.3. Basic work flow of WEKA Tool

Relying on the form of machine studying model that we use to expand, we should select any of the options which include Classify, Cluster, or partner. We are able to automatically choose any of the identical. WEKA presents the implementation of several algorithms and we can analyze every one in every of them separately. As stated, pick out an algorithm of your personal choice and set the favored enter and run it at the dataset. You may observe diverse models at the same dataset. You can then examine the outputs of different fashions and choose the excellent that meets your prediction.

- To install WEKA visit the official site, download the exe file and install it in the system.
- Open the WEKA tool and you will see the subsequent screen.

Fig.4. Explorer window

D. Implementation

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1 @relation data
2 @attribute MchlyHHIncome numeric
3 @attribute MchlyHHExpense numeric
4 @attribute NoofFlyMembers numeric
5 @attribute EmisPentAmt numeric
6 @attribute AnnualHHIncome numeric
7 @attribute HighestQualifieMember numeric
8 @attribute NoofKazningMembers {UnderGraduate, Illiterate, Graduate, PostGraduate}
9 @attribute class {no, yes}
10
11 @data
12 5000,8000,3,2000,64200,UnderGraduate,1,no
13 6000,7000,2,3000,79920,Illiterate,1,no
14 10000,4500,2,0,112800,UnderGraduate,1,yes
15 10000,2000,1,0,97200,Illiterate,1,yes
16 12500,12000,2,3000,147000,Graduate,1,yes
17 14000,6000,2,0,196560,Graduate,1,yes
18 15000,16000,3,35000,167400,PostGraduate,1,no
19 19000,20000,5,8000,216000,Graduate,1,no
20 19000,9000,2,0,218880,UnderGraduate,1,yes
21 20000,9000,4,0,228800,UnderGraduate,2,yes
22 20000,18000,4,8000,279400,UnderGraduate,2,yes
23 22000,25000,6,12000,279840,Illiterate,1,no
24 23400,5000,3,0,292032,Illiterate,1,yes
25 24000,10500,6,0,316000,Graduate,2,yes
26 24000,10000,4,0,244000,Graduate,2,yes
    
```

Fig.5. Dataset after converting into CSV format

- The above data shows the CSV file. This file is then inserted to the Weka tool extract the best output.
- Open the Weka tool and after that we need to click on at the Explorer. Pick the pre technique and from there select the dataset in CSV format which you need.
- Click the ‘open file’ and select the appropriate dataset you need.

IV. EXPERIMENT RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 6. Preprocessing window

Fig.7. After preprocessing data.

Fig. 8. After applying the Random Forest Algorithm.

Random Forest Algorithm is a type of supervised mastering algorithm, which may be used for classification and regression. It is higher than single decision tree.

- Correctly Classified Instances 45 90 %
- Incorrectly Classified Instances 5 10 %
- Kappa statistic 0
- Mean absolute error 0.1296
- Root mean squared error 0.2693
- Relative absolute error 66.2162 %
- Root relative squared error 88.5377 %
- Total Number of Instances 50

Table 1. Detailed Accuracy by class

	TP R a t e	FP R a t e	Preci s i o n	Recal l
	0.000	0.000	?	0.000
	1.000	1.000	0.900	1.000
Wei gh t e d A v g	0.900	0.900	?	0.900

Fig. 9. After applying Logistic model tree (LMT)

LMT is a classification model that is associated with supervised gaining knowledge of set of rules which mixes the properties of both decision tree and logistic regression.

• Incorrectly Classified Instances	5	10%
• Correctly Classified Instances	45	90%
• Kappa statistic	0	
• Mean absolute error	0.1296	
• Root mean squared error	0.2693	
• Relative absolute error	66.2162 %	
• Root relative squared error	88.5377 %	
• Total Number of Instances	50	

Table 2. Detailed Accuracy by class

	TP R a t e	FP R a t e	Preci s i o n	Recal l

	0.800	0.044	0.667	0.800
	0.956	0.200	0.977	0.956
Weighted Avg	0.940	0.184	0.946	0.940

V. RESULT ANALYSIS

We have collected dataset and converted it to the format which is understandable by WEKA tool. After that we have applied various classification algorithm on collected dataset to predict the income and expense ratio using the WEKA tool. As per the result shown in table 1, figure 5 and 6 we found that LMT algorithm gives the highest accuracy among all other algorithms.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Information mining carry out the very vital function for prediction of earnings and expenditure of a own family. statistics mining techniques and techniques helps own family participants for taking important choice-making method. in this research paper, we have implemented numerous class algorithms of facts mining for predicting. To perform the information mining analysis we've got amassed facts set which in particular encompass monthly earnings fees, month-to-month income, every year income, every year fees, highest academic qualifications and total variety of human beings incomes within the family.

Via applying this predictions a human beings can plan numerous techniques to control their costs. We also got here to recognize that people with more academic qualification have more profits.

VII. REFRECES

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